

■ *pla*
 ■ *pst* (pPCP1)
 ■ *yopD* (pCD1)
 ■ *YPMT1.67c* (pMT1)
 ■ *YPO3619* (Chromosome)

Medieval Latvia - G701

95% family-wise confidence level

